

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF CUSTOMS TERMINOLOGY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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***Abstract:** This article analysis the term of customs and the linguistic method of their as well as specific linguistic peculiarities of English customs terms touched upon and their lexical-semantically features were revealed such as the phenomena of ambiguity reveals the problems of their solutions in using these terms reflecting new semantic meanings of the terminological system and English customs terms brought into the terminological system based oncognition has become especially essential at this time.*

***Keywords:** lexicology, system of term development in customs affairs, terminological system, customs, product, custom sphere*

The study of Customs terminology from a young perspective from a linguistic standpoint determines its importance around the world. Because there is a direct general linguistic connection, there is a lexical-semantic process between English and Uzbek customs terminology and common literary language. Expression that contribute to the stylistically colored and appealing representation of speech. We can observe presence of stylistically colored terms in English terminology of taxation and customs area. They closely link to the terms of Customs sphere and are used as a form of combined special term. We classified common literary words according to the 5 sub-headings. Now, we analyze them which function both areas, in common literary and in Customs terminological system.

BRAKE

- Let's assume the lexeme **Brake**. **Brake** is a widely used word that means a device for slowing or stopping a moving vehicle, typically by applying pressure to

the wheels in the common literary language means

“**tormoz/brake**”.

Example:

She jumped with both feet onto her brake, casting up a rooster tail of snow behind the sled. The rig and team slowed. She stood straighter atop the runners

The word “**brake**” is expressing the part of a vehicle in the example shown above. This word is used in common literary in order to express a mechanical devise that inhibits motion absorbing energy from a moving system. It is used for slowing or stopping a moving vehicle, wheel, axle.

The word **brake** doesn't have figurative meaning when it is used in common literary; on the contrary it is expressed by denotative meaning. But as a result of combining this lexeme with special term **custom**, the word combination **custom break** can be formed.

But we shouldn't confuse the **tax break** with its paronymtax break. Actually, their pronunciation is the same, very close, similar though meaning is different. Definition of the term tax break is a “tax concession or advantage allowed by government”. If the government gives a tax break to a particular group of people or type of organization, it reduces the amount of tax they have to pay or changes the tax system in a way that benefits them.

For Example:

There is still a large uncertainty regarding the final decision on the tax breaks and possible implications for Vankor project and we expect Rosneft's stock to continue be volatile in the upcoming weeks.

SHIELD

• As well as the word widely used **shield**. Its lexical meaning is “**qalqon - shield**”. Its definition is as following in common literary language.

Shield - is a broad piece of metal or another suitable material, held by straps or a handle attached on one side, used as a protection against blows or missiles. We may describe it with additional explanation and examples. **Shield** is that something or

someone which is a **shield** against a particular danger or risk provides protection from it.

For Example:

The ozone layer is a **shield** which protects the Earth against the sun's radiation;

We don't notice connotative (figurative sense) meaning of the word shield when it is used in common literary language. But this word has many expressive meanings as follows.

Example

The fuzz flashed his shield and I knew the game was over – (shield means badge here). If you're a cop, where's your shield? – (shield means nameplate, number plate here).

But when we come across the word combination **tax shield** in context it means “ – **lowering of custom burden**”, “ – tax allowance/tax preference”, – protecting of paying taxes”. The synonyms of the word combination tax shield are tax deduction, tax credit, tax umbrella, depreciation tax shield, interest tax shield, tax planning etc... variants in translation. Dictionaries provide the following translations: As well, in some contexts (the analysis of financial leases, for example) depreciation tax shields are treated as safe, nominal cash flows and are discounted at an after tax borrowing or lending rate.

BARRIER

• The word widely used barrier, lexical meaning of the word in general literary language is “**to'siq-barrier**, hurdle, bar, locking”. Its literary definition as following.

First definition: **Barrier** - is a fence or other obstacle that prevents movement or access.

Second definition: A **barrier** is something such as a rule, law, or policy that makes it difficult or impossible for something to happen or be achieved. The word widely used barrier can be used in different situation in common literary language. For example, it may be:

- language barrier
- mountain barrier
- racial barrier
- sound / sonic barrier
- psychological barrier
- barrier against infection
- to overcome all the barriers
- custom-house barriers
- duties and taxes are the most obvious barrier to free trade;

Situation Disability need not be a barrier to a successful career; We have put up a real barrier against the outbreak of new wars; This paste provides a hygiene barrier against microbes

As a result of combining the barrier with the word “**customs**”absolutelyanother special term may be emerged. The word combination “**custom barrier**” means that restricting of import goods by increasing **customs duties**”.

We can cite as examples the following terms signifying expressivity in Custom lexis: pill poison means “pill, tablet, pill poisoning”. But it means as a special term "protection measures by the company against certain threats, particularly against bankruptcy". As well as sleeping beauty as a special term means “hegemon company (enterprise)”. The literal or word by word translation of combined word “tax eater” means "a person who eats a tax" in expressiveness, but it means as a special term “a person who lives through state subsidies”.

Laundering

- "erasing linen",
- Money laundering, appropriation of funds through crime,
- The elimination of the original source of funds. Particularly: laundering of dough in customs house.

For Example

The key to any money laundering scheme is to get the money into legitimate bank accounts without alerting lawenforcement officials to the money’s illicit past. Once the money is in a legitimate account, it can be transferred around the world without interference from the authorities

Thus, the interaction of customs terminologies with other types of terminology is a complex process during which natural language words go through a deep stage of conceptual process. Based on the foregoing, we can conclude that when using the terms of the customs spheres from English, it is necessary to pay special attention not only to the lexical, but also to the semantic features of these words. Ideas about the material world among different peoples are largely similar. In that case, a certain stylistic unit of one language, figuratively expressing a particular concept, may not have its exact equivalent in the stylistic system of another language. Therefore, stylistic and lexical features are an indispensable component of the process and requires the researcher to know the peculiarities of the vocabulary and stylistics of both languages.

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